

RoboCup Rescue 2026 Team Description Paper

UruBots

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Info

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Abstract—This paper describes the proposed methodology by Team UruBots for attending the 2026 RoboCup Rescue Robot League competition. Compared to our previous robotic platforms, the proposed system incorporates a modular robotic manipulator mounted on a quadruped platform, enabling mobile manipulation capabilities in rescue-like environments. Our system integrates locomotion, perception, SLAM, detection of QR codes and Hazmat symbols, and object manipulation within a unified ROS 2 framework. The manipulator was designed, projected and developed in-house using Dynamixel XL430 and XM430 actuators combined with external planetary gear reduction stages, allowing enhanced torque performance for interaction tasks. Our proposed approach is open source and we aim to contribute to the RoboCup Rescue community by combining robust quadruped mobility with integrated manipulation and perception.

Index Terms—RoboCup Rescue, Team Description Paper, Urban Search and Rescue, Autonomous Exploration.

I. INTRODUCTION

TTEAM UruBots was established in 2022 at the Technological University of Uruguay, campus of Rivera. UruBots participated in the RoboCup Robot Rescue League competition for the first time in 2025, achieving the fourth overall place, and a First in Class Mobility Award. The team has also attended the FIRA Roboworld Cup competitions of 2023 and 2024, where first place was achieved in the Mission Impossible league in 2023 and third place in both the Autonomous Car and Humanoids Leagues in 2024. [1], [2], [3] and in research [4], [5], [6], [7], [8].

In contrast to our previous robotic systems, which were primarily focused on autonomous navigation and perception, the 2026 platform introduces active manipulation capabilities through the integration of a custom robotic arm with dynamixel motors. [9], [10]. This addition enables interaction with objects in the environment, and enhanced inspection capabilities, which are critical requirements in search and rescue missions.

Our proposed robotics system is based on the use of a quadruped robot, chosen for its movement ability, both in flat and non-flat terrains. The robot is equipped with a camera and a LiDAR to perform perception and segmentation of

Fig. 1. Mobile platform: Go2 Robot.

objects. We have improved the robots' software system based on Robotics Operating System 2 (ROS2) with a mission planner that combines different packages of mapping, navigation, manipulation, and perception to perform rescue-related tasks. Overall, our proposed robotic solution for the RoboCup Rescue League 2026 can be seen in Figure 1.

A. Scientific Publications

Since 2022, our team has conducted research in areas closely related to rescue environments and robotic autonomy [4], [5], [8]. In Deniz et al. [4], we presented a real-time robotic situational awareness system for accident prevention in industrial settings. A ROS-based package was developed to perform autonomous navigation while integrating object detection using a YOLO-based model. This allowed the system

to identify unsafe conditions, such as the absence of safety equipment and provide alerts to the user. Although focused on industrial applications, this work directly relates to rescue scenarios, as it combines autonomous navigation, perception, and contextual understanding.

In Moraes et al. [5], we conducted a study of convolutional neural networks for autonomous navigation of a mini autonomous vehicle using behavior cloning. The study demonstrated that architectural modifications, such as adding or removing specific layers, could improve navigation performance under certain conditions. This work strengthened our expertise in deep learning methods and autonomous control strategies. Additionally, Grando et al. [8] demonstrated that Reinforcement Learning can enhance autonomous navigation performance in mobile robots. By introducing delayed learning strategies in the RL agent, the system achieved reliable performance in goal-oriented tasks across both known and previously unseen environments.

The team has also participated in local research events [11], [12], presenting developments related to human–robot interaction and object detection. Furthermore, we highlight previous Team Description Papers submitted to other robotics competitions, including works focused on mini autonomous cars [3] and unmanned aerial vehicles [1]. In [3], we proposed a machine learning-based approach for autonomous car navigation, while in [1], we implemented visual odometry techniques to address navigation-related challenges in aerial robotics.

II. HARDWARE DESCRIPTION

This section will present the proposed hardware description for the RoboCup 2026 Rescue competition. Our mechanical and hardware setup was done with the objective of being able to tackle tasks of the competitions and to have space for adaptations in case of necessity during the competition week.

A. Robotic Platform

The robotic platform used in this work is the Unitree Go2 Pro [13]. This quadruped robot, developed by Unitree Robotics, features an advanced integration of hardware and software that includes a 4D LiDAR sensor, an RGB-D camera, onboard computing (8-core Intel-based embedded system), and a 12-degree-of-freedom leg system, enabling dynamic mobility and autonomy. The system is fully compatible with ROS 2, allowing for applications such as SLAM, navigation, and real-time perception. Table I provides a detailed description of the components and technical specifications of the robotic platform.

The robot can be operated in a manual or autonomous setting, allowing it to be controlled with an external operator or through an onboard autonomous package. The vehicle has several navigation modules, allowing it to be set for navigation in plain terrains, steep terrains and in scenarios with obstacles and stairs. The components of our robotic platform can be seen in Table I.

TABLE I
TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF OUR ROBOTIC PLATFORM

Attribute	Value
Name	Unitree Go2 Pro
Overall Dimensions	700 × 310 × 400 mm
Weight (with battery)	15 kg
Payload	8 kg (MAX 10–12 kg)
Max Speed	Up to 3.7 m/s (MAX 5.0 m/s)
Max Climb Angle	40°
Max Obstacle Height	16 cm
Drive Type	12 DOF Legged System (BLDC Motors)
Peak Joint Torque	Up to 45 N·m
LiDAR	Unitree 4D LiDAR L1 (360° × 90°)
Front Camera	1280 × 720, FOV 120°, ultra-wide-angle lens
IPC	8-core onboard CPU
Battery	33.6 V, 8000 mAh
Endurance	1–2 h (standard), 2–4 h (long battery)
Charger	33.6 V – 3.5 A
Operating System	Customized Ubuntu
ROS Version	ROS 2 Humble
App Control Range	~30 m
Control Method	Mobile App / Remote Controller / ROS 2

B. Robotic Manipulator

The robotic arm mounted over the robotic platform was based on an open project [14], which was used as a reference and further improved with several parts to accommodate it over our mobile robot. We made mechanical improvements to improve structural rigidity. Some of the changes made to the reference model include improvement on tolerances and the length of the arm segments to accommodate for torque capability. Overall, Fig. 2 shows our proposed robotic arm.

Fig. 2. Proposed mounted robotic arm.

Likewise, the design criteria was inspired by the commercial PincherX-100 manipulator [15], particularly with regard to the

modular configuration and arrangement of the actuators for the joints 3 to 5.

1) *Mechanical Architecture*: The manipulator is composed of six actuated joints that define its kinematic chain, with a *gripper*-type grasping mechanism as the end effector. This arrangement provides five degrees of freedom for end-effector positioning and orientation, in addition to grasping capability. The chain of joints is described as follows:

- **J0**: Base axial rotation
- **J1**: Shoulder pitch
- **J2**: Elbow pitch
- **J3**: Wrist axial rotation
- **J4**: Wrist pitch
- **J5**: Gripper actuation

The structure was primarily manufactured using additive manufacturing with reinforced structural PLA. Since serial manipulators operate in a cantilever configuration, additional reinforcements were incorporated at joints J0, J1, and J2, where the highest bending moments and dynamic loads are concentrated. These modifications improved structural stability without significantly penalizing the overall system weight.

2) *Actuators and Gear Reduction System*: The system employs Dynamixel XL430-W250 and XM430-W350 smart actuators [16], selected due to their embedded electronic integration, digital position and current control, TTL communication interface, and absolute position feedback with a resolution of 4096 steps per revolution. The use of smart actuators significantly reduces overall electronic system complexity while enabling direct implementation of kinematic control within the ROS 2 framework.

However, considering that the manipulator is mounted on a mobile platform and frequently operates in extended configurations, the nominal actuator torque shown to be insufficient under high load conditions during trials. To mitigate this limitation, a planetary gear reduction stages were incorporated in the critical joints (J0, J1, and J2), thereby increasing output torque and improving structural stability during manipulation tasks. Fig. 3 presents the proposed planetary gear system used in our manipulator.

The manipulator power system consists of a 26 V primary battery and a 20 A DC–DC converter responsible for generating a regulated 12 V supply line for the actuators. Raspberry Pi and peripherals are powered by an independent 5V, 20Ah power supply. Finally the Go2 robot uses 33,6V/8Ah.

3) *Electronic and Control Architecture*: The system is based on a Raspberry Pi 5, which serves as the main processing unit, receiving peripheral data, such as the manipulator camera. Communication with the actuators is established through a U2D2 interface that converts USB signals to the TTL protocol required by the Dynamixel motors, forming a shared serial communication bus.

ROS 2 nodes running on the Raspberry Pi are responsible for kinematic computation, joint trajectory planning, and actuator communication management. This architecture enables the manipulator to operate as a modular subsystem within a unified robotic platform. The robotic platform (Go2) and the arm maintain independence in low-level control, both communicating with the Raspberry Pi.

Fig. 3. Planetary gear system

The manipulator integrates an RGB camera mounted on its structure for local perception tasks, enabling future implementation of vision-guided manipulation strategies. For the competition week, we aim to have a ROS2 package with the robots' kinematics and an integrated vision setup that allows autonomous manipulation as well.

C. Processing and Communication Platform

The Unitree Go2 Pro is equipped with an onboard CPU featuring eight processing cores, designed to handle real-time control and perception tasks. This computing unit manages core functionalities such as mobility control, sensor fusion, SLAM, and autonomous navigation.

The platform provides dual Gigabit Ethernet ports and a high-speed communication bus, enabling reliable integration with external processing units, development computers, or remote control interfaces. Unlike other platforms, the Go2 Pro does not offer USB expansion, emphasizing its streamlined and robust network-based architecture.

The Unitree Go2 Pro features robust wireless connectivity through dual-band WiFi 6, Bluetooth 5.2, and optional 4G/eSIM modules. These communication interfaces enable remote operation and telemetry transmission. The robot's internal data architecture is structured around a DDS middleware, which facilitates efficient communication between perception modules, control systems, and multimedia services.

External computing platforms or development boards can interface with the system through ROS 2, DDS, or GStreamer SDKs over Gigabit Ethernet, ensuring compatibility with standard robotics frameworks. The sensor suite includes Unitree's 4D LiDAR, Intel RealSense D435i depth cameras, and foot-end force sensors, enabling high-fidelity environmental awareness and interaction.

Figure 4 illustrates the communication topology of the Go2 Pro, including the interaction between the onboard modules, the cloud service, the Go app, and external development systems.

III. SOFTWARE

Our proposed software system is based on the Robotics Operating System, combining both existing and developed

Fig. 4. System electronics and communication topology.

packages. Each part of our software system is presented below.

A. Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM)

Our proposed SLAM is based on the RTAB-Map for ROS [17]. The SLAM system gets information from the LiDAR and the robot camera, where a map of a scenario was manually generated, as can be seen in Figure 5.

We used the robot’s package ¹ to manually create the map and use it as input for the robots’ SLAM. As can be seen in Figure 5, a target position can be defined through the RVIZ interface and also using the robots’ target position topic. Figure 5 shows the robot’s frame and then the calculated path toward a manually set target on the RVIZ interface.

Fig. 5. Mapping of a scenario using our robot.

B. Computer vision software

Video streams are acquired through network-based connections to both the camera mounted on the manipulator and the

¹https://github.com/unitreerobotics/unitree_ros2

camera integrated into the Go2 Robot. QR codes are processed using OpenCV-based detection algorithm and Hazardous materials (HAZMAT) symbology detection was implemented using a YOLOv8nano model trained for 90 epochs.

The detection software runs locally at the operator control center, where image data is received remotely over the network from the onboard cameras. The trained model performs real-time object detection on the incoming video streams. The system processes the frames and generates an overlay containing bounding boxes, class labels, and confidence scores corresponding to the detected elements.

C. Previous RoboCup Experience

Fig. 6. Our robotic system performing at the 2025 Robocup Rescue League.

In 2025, Team UruBots participated in the RoboCup Rescue League competition, where we obtained our highest score in the mobility evaluation category. The platform demonstrated robust locomotion performance across uneven terrain, obstacle

negotiation scenarios, and navigation tasks under time constraints. Fig. 6 shows our robot performing at Robocup 2025.

Fig. 7. Timeframe of our robot performing in Robocup 2025 and in our qualification video.

The mobility score reflected the stability and adaptability of our quadruped configuration, particularly in scenarios involving ramps, debris simulation, and constrained passages. Through testing and iterative improvements, we optimized gait parameters, balance control, and navigation strategies to maximize efficiency and reliability.

This previous participation provided valuable insights into the operational demands of the RoboCup Rescue League, especially regarding mechanical robustness, energy management, and autonomous navigation in semi-structured environments. The experience gained in 2025 influenced the design decisions implemented in the 2026 platform, particularly in terms of structural reinforcement, modularity, and system integration.

Building upon our mobility performance, the current platform extends these capabilities by incorporating active manipulation, allowing the robot not only to traverse complex terrain but also to interact physically with objects in rescue-like scenarios.

IV. QUALIFICATION EXPERIMENT

According to the competition's theme of rescue tasks, a scenario was developed where the robot should navigate to a specific desired point. For that, in our qualification video, it is possible to visualize our robot performing tasks demanded at the competition. Figure 7 shows our proposed system performing in our qualification video.

In our qualification video, we demanded our robot navigate in a steep scenario, performing the task of detecting sensory information and performing real-time manipulation of objects, such as inserting an object in a small hole.

The training scenario was made using multiple items, such as pallets, wooden boxes, and layers of foam mat tiles. The training ground tried to be as similar as possible to previously used ones in the actual competitions, although due to space and material limitations, it was not possible to replicate the exact conditions, mainly the highly steep slopes and obstacles.

V. CONCLUSION

In this team description paper, we provide the approach of our team for the 2026 Robocup Rescue League. We focus on bringing together existing hardware and software to provide a reliable solution to attend the competition. Through the experiments performed and the methodology presented, we aim to attend the competition for the second time, looking forward to learning and contributing to the league's development.

APPENDIX A

TEAM MEMBERS AND THEIR CONTRIBUTIONS

Many students and researchers at the Technological University of Uruguay contribute to the team. The following list as it appears in the author's list:

- Kevin Farias Hardware Setup
- Santiago Martin Software and communications
- Vinicio Melgar Mechanical Setup and computer vision
- Pablo Moraes Manipulator design
- Juan Deniz SLAM and ROS2 integration
- Bárbara Flores Manipulator kinematics modeling
- Antonhy Picanzo Software Development
- Hiago Sodre Testing, editing and footage
- Sebastian Barcelona Software Development
- Ricardo Grando Software Development

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